

Data Ethics, Integrity, and Security in Shared Cloud Platforms

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Abstract: *The current study describes how organizations can maintain data integrity and security in their shared cloud platforms. The literature review describes data integrity to be crucial in influencing the operations achieved by a business. This is attributed to effective decision-making from the data obtained from the shared cloud platform. This showcases the need for shared cloud platforms to promote their data integrity. The theoretical framework is effective and ensures that the entire research process has been guided by the framework selected. The findings in the study support that data integrity can be maintained through various methods and actions.*

Keywords: *Data integrity, security, Ethical use, shared cloud platforms, data completeness.*

Introduction

Data is the new gold and with the evolution of cloud computing, the importance of data processing and insights extraction has increased manyfold in the last decade (Dash & Gatharia, 2015). Cloud computing has been a revolutionary technology for most businesses today. Many businesses today adopt cloud computing applications to promote development (Almorsy et al., 2011). This has promoted the rise of different types of cloud applications. Cloud platforms describe the hardware and system users access through the internet (Goyal, 2014). There is a vast list of cloud platforms supported by various companies today (Awada & Barker, 2017). These companies offer different types of services and access to their cloud systems.

Morden business is very competitive, it is about data-driven decision-making and strategic role-playing (Dash & Agarwal, 2016). Shared cloud platforms engage a shared infrastructure where services can be accessed by different companies. However, a private cloud platform is personal to the organization that developed the cloud platform (Goyal, 2014). Shared cloud platforms have become increasingly popular, with many companies hosting public clouds for users to rent and access. The public clouds are considered cheaper and more effective for businesses that do not require extensive personal use of their cloud. Some of the most popular shared cloud platforms today include AWS by Amazon, Google Cloud by Google, and Azure by Microsoft (Goyal, 2014).

Data integrity and security are crucial elements in every cloud platform. Data integrity focuses on three key components. Data integrity describes the completeness, accuracy, and consistency of data in the system. Data integrity is crucial in promoting the validity of data and its overall usefulness (Yu et al., 2017). Companies depend on data integrity because it helps them make more effective and reliable decisions. Incomplete or inaccurate data is considered dangerous for a business's decision (Yu et al., 2017). Figure 1 below identifies the key components crucial in promoting data integrity.

Figure 1: Elements in Data Integrity

Security is the next element needed to promote data integrity. Data integrity requires that data has been stored safely and cannot be exploited by unauthorized individuals (Almorsy et al., 2011). The security of the data especially becomes crucial in a shared cloud platform. Businesses hold a lot of sensitive information that should not be accessed by their competitors. This information should be kept secure in all instances to protect the business. The need to promote the data integrity of their information is a crucial element when selecting a shared cloud platform. Despite this knowledge, limited research explores how businesses can effectively maintain data integrity and security in shared cloud platforms.

Research Question: How can organizations promote data integrity, and data security and follow data ethics in shared cloud platforms?

Literature Review

A shared cloud platform describes a cloud computing platform in which the clients control the applications and services offered, but the cloud platform is owned by a different organization. Microsoft Azure is a good example of a shared cloud platform (Awada & Barker, 2017). Customers can pay for specific applications and tools which they have control over. Microsoft, however, maintains the control and developments implemented towards the shared cloud platform. These platforms are considered crucial to businesses and differ from private cloud platforms.

The public cloud platforms are very important to businesses but have several concerns that should be addressed. The responsibility for the development and management of these platforms is always associated with the public cloud provider. Microsoft Azure, for example, is only managed by Microsoft company (Hawedi et al., 2018). Companies that request services from public cloud platforms commonly focus on extra or backup storage for their data. The customers can use the shared cloud platform to ensure their company's data has been backed up.

Although shared cloud platforms are increasingly popular, there are significant challenges that businesses need to consider (Dash & Gatheria, 2015). Security concerns are crucial because businesses store sensitive information on these platforms. Most public cloud providers promise that their systems are secure and that the information cannot be accessed by unauthorized users (Yu et al., 2017). However, customers are always advised to implement measures to monitor malware and unauthorized access to the information presented (Garg & Bawa, 2016). Many business leaders, however, remain unaware of what actions they could take toward promoting their

data integrity. Figure 2 below identifies the importance of data integrity for an organization's operations.

Figure 2: Importance of Data Integrity

Cloud computing platforms are required to promote data integrity. Data integrity is identified as a crucial element that influences the decisions made by a business (Almorsy et al., 2011). Better decisions in the business also impact the operations adopted by the business leaders. Figure 2 above identifies the relationship between these concepts.

Luo & Bai (2011) describe that shared cloud platforms have the main data integrity issue. The impact of the integrity of the data in shared platforms makes them ineffective as a crucial tool for businesses. The article by Luo & Bai (2011) identifies that businesses must implement measures and solutions that can help maintain their data integrity. The article identifies that remote checking protocol is one of the solutions that businesses can take in promoting the data integrity of their information in shared cloud platforms.

Gorg & Bawa (2016) focused on some of the system models that have been introduced in promoting data integrity for shared cloud platforms. The study reviews the models currently employed in most public cloud platforms. Gorg & Bawa (2016) found that most data integrity auditing protocols were inefficient. These models are shown to have been ineffective in encountering all the properties associated with cloud platforms. The authors recommend that future studies focus on ways customers can maintain data integrity.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The Task Technology Fit (TTF) model is used to guide the research process for this research. The TTF framework identifies that the utilization of technology is promoted by the technology's ability to reach the users' tasks and requirements (Wu & Chen, 2017). TTF also holds that IT can have more impact if it attains the eight factors associated with systems. Wu & Chen (2017, p.222) suggests that "the eight factors in TTF include quality, locatable, authorization, compatibility, ease of use/training, timeliness, reliability and relationship with the users." The theory holds that users would benefit more from a system that holds each of the factors identified above. These factors represent the components of data integrity. The importance of data integrity in shared cloud platforms is described using the TTF (Wu & Chen, 2017). The TTF model identifies that the shared cloud platforms are more likely to have more outcomes if the above factors have been met. These factors showcase the importance of data integrity towards the system's usefulness. Figure 3 below identifies the model and how data integrity reflects the impact and quality identified from a system.

Figure 3: TTF Model

Data Collection

The research employs a critical review approach with an effective sample size which is important for better outcomes of our testing. Rightly, the research question and effective sample size are very critical to observing a better outcome (Dash & Ali, 2019). The approach focuses on qualitative data from secondary research studies. The articles referenced were obtained from well-respected journals on the internet. The inclusion criteria focused on studies describing how to promote data integrity and some of the challenges experienced with shared cloud platforms. The keywords used in searching for these articles were "Data Integrity," "Shared Cloud Platforms," and "data security in the cloud." The keywords provided dozens of articles, which were then screened to determine whether they answered the research question. The articles were also exempted if they were published a long time ago. The screening criteria are aimed at improving the study's reliability and validity. The collected data was then analyzed to provide key information to answer the study's research question.

Results and Discussion

The studies obtained showed that there are several challenges associated with cloud computing, and more specifically, with shared cloud platforms. Data security is one of the main challenges with shared cloud platforms. Companies always place significant data in these shared cloud platforms (Luo & Bai, 2011). The lack of visibility and control tools challenges the ability of a business to ensure the security of its data has been obtained personally. The company also hands over the accountability for any security outcomes their data experiences in the shared platforms. Therefore, any risks associated with the data can not be controlled, indicating a significant challenge for business.

Malware and antiviruses within the shared cloud platforms also risk the quality of data stored in the shared cloud platforms. Shared cloud platforms are public cloud platforms. Significant risks are associated with contaminated data from other data sets stored in the same cloud platform (He et al., 2014). The concerns over malware and data security prove that data integrity is a significant challenge with shared cloud platforms (Albugmi et al., 2016). The clients cannot prove the

integrity of the data and information stored on the shared cloud platforms. These challenges should be addressed for businesses to be impacted by the shared cloud systems.

Data integrity is identified to rely on several components that should be met. These components include data completeness, data accuracy, data consistency, and data security (Wang et al., 2012). Various studies support that data integrity promotes more effective decision-making and improves the operational ability within a business (Yu et al., 2017). The studies also identify that managers are required to ensure their data integrity has been improved. This especially becomes critical in shared cloud platforms where data backup is included.

Public cloud providers must integrate a culture of data integrity across their platforms. This is one of the solutions necessary in maintaining data integrity within shared cloud platforms (Albugmi et al., 2016). A culture of integrity can be achieved through employee training within these organizations (Yu et al., 2017). Employees must become aware of their roles and responsibilities toward attaining data integrity. This will help promote data integrity within the organizations.

Introducing data validation is another critical action necessary for maintaining data integrity (Sathyanarayana & Sheela, 2013; Sharma, 2016). Data validation is effective because it helps prevent malware and viruses on shared cloud platforms (Hawedi et al., 2018; Dash, 2017). The approach effectively protects the vast amount of data within the cloud platform from being impacted by malware.

The security associated with data in the shared cloud platforms can also be improved through advanced hardware systems (Kmari et al., 2018). The hardware system is a crucial part of the cloud platforms. Public cloud providers must implement effective technologies that ensure data security has been maintained (Luo & Bai, 2011). Data integrity is also maintained by ensuring no frequent failures associated with the hardware. Users must have access to their data when they request the information at any location.

Businesses must also implement several actions to maintain data integrity and security. Businesses should train their employees on proper policies associated with data integrity. Encrypting the data stored on shared cloud platforms is an effective approach for maintaining data security (Hawedi et al., 2018). Businesses with encrypted information on shared cloud platforms are more likely to protect their information. The employees should understand the importance of encryption and that all information stored on the shared cloud platforms has been protected from possible attacks (Sathyanarayana & Sheela, 2013).

Data integrity can also be promoted by controlling the accessibility to the data. Authorized access minimizes data tampering (Rao & Selvamani, 2015). Authorized access to the shared cloud platform is an effective approach that allows a business to keep logs of all modifications done to the data (Garg & Bawa, 2016). Authorized access also prevents the data from being accidentally deleted from the company's database. These policies are crucial for a business because they help reduce tampering and impacts on the company's information.

Garg & Bawa (2016) indicate that cloud data integrity auditing protocols are effective software tools companies could use to maintain the integrity of their data on the shared cloud. The data integrity auditing tools engage in several protocols where a business can check whether the information stored is secure and of the required quality (Kmari et al., 2018). Garg & Bawa (2016) describe that dozens of data integrity auditing tools are available on the internet. These tools are

considered very effective in meeting the businesses' requirements (Yu et al., 2016; Sharma, 2017). Businesses can identify what factors they require and, therefore, implement an effective system that meets their needs and protects their information.

Conclusion

Data integrity is a crucial factor in the way businesses operate today. Data integrity is crucial because of the dependence on data to make informed decisions. Shared cloud platforms are, however, showcased to present a significant challenge to data integrity. Security concerns are a significant risk associated with using shared cloud platforms. The studies analyzed identified that companies are required to effectively adopt approved methods and techniques needed to maintain data integrity. The discussion section identifies some actions public cloud providers and businesses could adopt to maintain data integrity and security. Each method described is crucial for improving data integrity and promoting productivity through effective decision-making.

The data presented several limitations which should be addressed in future studies. The first limitation identified was that the data integrated a few numbers of resources for analysis. Future research studies should consider more articles for the analysis. The next limitation identified is that the study primarily obtained data from secondary research. Future studies should engage in primary research methods aimed at obtaining primary findings. These findings are more reliable in understanding the state of shared cloud platforms today.

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